

Survey: Open research at Oxford

Version 2.0

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Content

This is a survey developed by members of the Reproducible Research Oxford steering group (<https://ox.ukrn.org/>), and administered at the University of Oxford between 13th January 2022 and 1st March 2022. The aim of this survey is to assess the views of researchers on open research practices, related training needs and provision, and recruitment criteria to inform the implementation of open research practices and responsible research assessment at Oxford.

Page 2 to 26: survey 'Open research at Oxford'

Page 27: form to enter a raffle for a chance to win vouchers

Acknowledgment

We are grateful to Rhea Arini, Lotte Boon, Tanita Casci, Kathryn Dally, Richard Duszanskyj, Emily Farran, David Gavaghan, Megan Gooch, Cassandra Gould Van Praag, Verena Heise, Matthew Jaquiere, Sven Kasser, Adam Kenny, Alexander Kirchner-Häusler, Thibault Lestang, Ruth Mallalieu, David Mellor, Brian Nosek, Christopher Osborne, Meriel Patrick, Ilse Pit, Susanna-Assunta Sansone, Iveta Simera, and Rowan Wilson, for their helpful contributions to development of the survey.

Open research at Oxford

Broadly, open research (also called ‘open scholarship’ or, in some disciplines, ‘open science’) refers to efforts to ensure that different elements of the research process are transparent and accessible. The aim of this survey is to assess the views of Oxford researchers on **open research practices**, related **training needs and provision**, and **recruitment criteria**.

The survey is administered by [Reproducible Research Oxford](#). It is aimed at researchers in any role and at any career stage (including **academics**, **research staff** and **fellows**, **research support staff**, and **postgraduate research students**), working in **any field of research** across the collegiate University. The target audience includes researchers based in **all Divisions** of the University (Humanities; Mathematical, Physical, and Life Sciences; Medical Sciences; Social Sciences; Gardens, Libraries and Museums; Continuing Education) and/or in the **Colleges**.

Survey responses will inform the implementation of open research practices and responsible research assessment at Oxford. Therefore, it is important for **all views** to be represented. You are encouraged to take part whether or not you are aware of open research practices, and whether or not you deem them relevant or necessary for your field of research. Your participation will ensure that related guidance developed at departmental and/or University level is appropriate for your discipline.

As a ‘thank you’ for taking part, we will donate £1 to the University’s [Graduate Student Support Fund](#) for each survey submitted (up to a total of £1,500). Additionally, after completing the survey you can enter a raffle for a chance to win one of **five £50 gift cards** from [Bookshop.org](#), an online service in support of local bookshops (optional; details below).

Between January and March 2021 we administered the survey to postgraduate research students. Following that round, we donated £500 to the University’s Coronavirus Hardship Fund, and we awarded five £50 Blackwell’s gift cards to respondents who entered the raffle. The results have been used to inform the work of Reproducible Research Oxford and related activities in the University, and they will be compared to the results from the current round. If you already took part in the survey, thank you for your contribution! You are welcome to take part again.

Survey procedure and data protection

Participation in the survey is **voluntary**. The survey comprises **12 questions**, and we estimate that it will take under **20 minutes** to complete. You can complete part of the survey and resume it on this device, using the same browser, within seven days. The survey will be active until 1 March 2022.

You can choose to exit the survey at any time. Additionally, you can explicitly request to **withdraw** your responses while the survey is active, whether you have completed it in full or only in part. Once you agree to participate, you will be provided with a respondent ID for this purpose (details below).

All responses will be **anonymous** and they will be used exclusively for academic purposes. Non-identifiable information will be shared openly in appropriate repositories, and relevant findings will be disseminated via the Reproducible Research Oxford website.

Once you complete the survey, you will be given access to a separate secure form. If you wish to enter the **raffle for the Bookshop.org's gift cards** (optional), you can provide your contact details in this form. The information provided will not be linked to your survey responses in any way. It will be stored securely and permanently deleted once all raffle prizes are accepted. We will not use the information for any other purpose.

Reproducible Research Oxford is supported by an interdivisional award from the John Fell Fund (award number: 0007132). Ethical review of all procedures linked to the survey was conducted following Central University Research Ethics Committee (CUREC) guidance (approval number: SAME_C1A_20_105, contact: hod@anthro.ox.ac.uk), and in line with University guidance on the requirements of data protection law.

Contact

If you have any comments or questions, please contact the Reproducible Research Oxford Coordinator, Dr Malika Ihle (malika.ihle@anthro.ox.ac.uk).

Consent

I consent to participating in the survey and to processing of the information I provide as outlined above.

Your respondent ID is: *Randomly generated number*

Should you wish to withdraw your responses at any time while the survey is active, please contact the Reproducible Research Oxford Coordinator, Dr Malika Ihle (malika.ihle@anthro.ox.ac.uk), quoting your respondent ID.

Personal information

This survey is aimed at researchers in any role and at any career stage (including academics, research staff and fellows, research support staff, and postgraduate research students), working in any field of research across all Divisions of the University of Oxford (excluding staff working in University Administration and Services) and/or in the Colleges.

Q1 Please select your primary affiliation at Oxford.

College-only staff

Please select the Division and department closest to your field of research.

Humanities Division

- Faculty of Classics
- Faculty of English Language and Literature
- Faculty of History
- Department of History of Art
- Faculty of Linguistics, Philology and Phonetics and Phonetics Laboratory
- Faculty of Medieval and Modern Languages
- Faculty of Music
- Faculty of Oriental Studies
- Faculty of Philosophy
- Faculty of Theology and Religion
- Institute for Ethics in AI
- The Oxford Research Centre in the Humanities
- Rothermere American Institute
- Ruskin School of Art
- Voltaire Foundation
- Other, please specify:

Mathematical, Physical, and Life Sciences Division

- Begbroke Science Park
- Department of Chemistry
- Department of Computer Science
- Department of Earth Sciences
- Department of Engineering Science
- Mathematical Institute
- Department of Materials
- Department of Physics
- Department of Plant Sciences
- Department of Statistics
- Department of Zoology
- Doctoral Training Centre
- Oxford e-Research Centre
- Other, please specify:

Medical Sciences Division

- o Department of Biochemistry
- o Nuffield Department of Clinical Medicine
- o Nuffield Department of Clinical Neurosciences
- o Department of Experimental Psychology
- o Radcliffe Department of Medicine
- o Nuffield Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology
- o Department of Oncology
- o Nuffield Department of Orthopaedics, Rheumatology and Musculoskeletal Sciences
- o Department of Paediatrics
- o Sir William Dunn School of Pathology
- o Department of Pharmacology
- o Department of Physiology, Anatomy and Genetics
- o Nuffield Department of Population Health
- o Nuffield Department of Primary Health Care Health Sciences
- o Department of Psychiatry
- o Nuffield Department of Surgical Sciences
- o Nuffield Department of Women's & Reproductive Health
- o Other, please specify:

o Social Sciences Division

- o School of Anthropology and Museum Ethnography
- o School of Archaeology
- o Blavatnik School of Government
- o Department of Economics
- o Department of Education
- o School of Geography and the Environment
- o School of Global and Area Studies
- o Department of International Development
- o Oxford Internet Institute
- o Faculty of Law
- o Oxford Martin School
- o Department of Politics and International Relations
- o Saïd Business School
- o Department of Social Policy and Intervention
- o Department of Sociology
- o Other, please specify:

o Gardens, Libraries and Museums

- o Ashmolean Museum
- o Bodleian Libraries
- o History of Science Museum
- o Museum of Natural History
- o Oxford Botanic Garden & Harcourt Arboretum
- o Pitt Rivers Museum
- o Other, please specify:

o Department for Continuing Education

o Humanities Division

- o Faculty of Classics
- o Faculty of English Language and Literature
- o Faculty of History
- o Department of History of Art
- o Faculty of Linguistics, Philology and Phonetics and Phonetics Laboratory
- o Faculty of Medieval and Modern Languages
- o Faculty of Music
- o Faculty of Oriental Studies
- o Faculty of Philosophy
- o Faculty of Theology and Religion
- o Institute for Ethics in AI
- o The Oxford Research Centre in the Humanities
- o Rothermere American Institute
- o Ruskin School of Art
- o Voltaire Foundation
- o Other, please specify:

o Mathematical, Physical, and Life Sciences Division

- o Begbroke Science Park
- o Department of Chemistry
- o Department of Computer Science
- o Department of Earth Sciences
- o Department of Engineering Science
- o Mathematical Institute
- o Department of Materials
- o Department of Physics
- o Department of Plant Sciences
- o Department of Statistics
- o Department of Zoology
- o Doctoral Training Centre
- o Oxford e-Research Centre
- o Other, please specify:

o Medical Sciences Division

- o Department of Biochemistry
- o Nuffield Department of Clinical Medicine
- o Nuffield Department of Clinical Neurosciences
- o Department of Experimental Psychology
- o Radcliffe Department of Medicine
- o Nuffield Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology

- o Department of Oncology
- o Nuffield Department of Orthopaedics, Rheumatology and Musculoskeletal Sciences
- o Department of Paediatrics
- o Sir William Dunn School of Pathology
- o Department of Pharmacology
- o Department of Physiology, Anatomy and Genetics
- o Nuffield Department of Population Health
- o Nuffield Department of Primary Health Care Health Sciences
- o Department of Psychiatry
- o Nuffield Department of Surgical Sciences
- o Nuffield Department of Women's & Reproductive Health
- o Other, please specify:

- o Social Sciences Division
 - o School of Anthropology and Museum Ethnography
 - o School of Archaeology
 - o Blavatnik School of Government
 - o Department of Economics
 - o Department of Education
 - o School of Geography and the Environment
 - o School of Global and Area Studies
 - o Department of International Development
 - o Oxford Internet Institute
 - o Faculty of Law
 - o Oxford Martin School
 - o Department of Politics and International Relations
 - o Saïd Business School
 - o Department of Social Policy and Intervention
 - o Department of Sociology
 - o Other, please specify:

- o Gardens, Libraries and Museums
 - o Ashmolean Museum
 - o Bodleian Libraries
 - o History of Science Museum
 - o Museum of Natural History
 - o Oxford Botanic Garden & Harcourt Arboretum
 - o Pitt Rivers Museum
 - o Other, please specify:

- o Department for Continuing Education

Q2 Please select your role at the University (or closest equivalent, for College-only staff).

We define staff roles based on the categories used by the University's Human Resources, namely:

- **Academic** (e.g. Associate Professor; Clinical Academic Staff; Clinical Lecturer; Departmental Lecturer; Professor; Reader; Head of Division)
- **Research Staff or Research Fellow** (e.g. Clinical Researcher; Postdoctoral Researcher; Postdoctoral Research Assistant; Research Associate; Research Council Fellow [Senior, Advanced, Postdoctoral]; Research Fellow; Royal Society Fellow; Royal Society Research Professor; Clinical Research Fellow; Wellcome Trust Fellow)
- **Research Support Staff** (e.g. Academic Clinical Trials Coordinator; Bioinformatician; Data Analyst; Statistician; Clinical Research Coordinator; Clinical Trials Coordinator/Officer/Manager; Knowledge Exchange Fellow/Officer; Laboratory Manager; Programme Manager; Research Analysis Officer; Research Project Manager; Research Coordinator; Research Facilitator; Science Liaison Officer; Science Officer; Theme Coordinator)

In addition to the staff roles above, the survey is aimed at **students on postgraduate research programmes** (PGR, e.g. MSc by Research; MPhil; DPhil; EPSRC CDT; NERC DTP; BBSRC DTP; DClinPsych), not at undergraduate students, nor at postgraduate students on taught courses (PGT, e.g. MSc; MPhil; MSt; MLitt; PGDip; MBA; EMBA).

- | |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"><input type="radio"/> Academic<input type="radio"/> Research Staff or Research Fellow<input type="radio"/> Research Support Staff<input type="radio"/> Student on a postgraduate research programme |
|--|

Q3 Please indicate the overall duration of your research experience (number of years rounded to the nearest 0.5 year).

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Open research practices

This section focuses on open research. Definitions of relevant terms vary across fields of research and contexts. Therefore, we provide the following standardised entries for you to refer to throughout the remainder of the survey.

Open Access publication An article, book chapter, book, or other scholarly work that is released with unrestricted access (i.e. available to the public to view online, or download, without registration, payment, or approval). This includes all forms of open access, such as 'green' (i.e. the accepted version of the work, after peer review, is shared by the author(s) in a repository), and 'gold' (i.e. the version processed by the publisher is released openly on the publisher's system upon publication).

Repository A service dedicated to facilitating the preservation and sharing of research content, including digital repositories (for digital collections, data, code, etc.) and physical repositories (for collections, archives, reagents, specimens, etc.). The service may be operated by universities, governments, or private organizations, and it can be domain-agnostic or discipline-specific. Access to such repositories may be open or controlled (e.g. requiring registration, payment, or approval). Personal web-pages or other ad hoc methods of storing and sharing research content are not included.

Data Any information underpinning a piece of research. The information can be qualitative (e.g. source, archive, representation of art, artefact) and/or quantitative (e.g. measurements, machine output, simulation results). The data can be raw (i.e. as collected), cleaned (i.e. corrected for errors), or prepared/processed (e.g. transformed into a different format for analysis, or anonymized for sharing).

Code Custom software developed by researchers specifically for the purpose of conducting a piece of research (e.g. a computer program to extract, clean, or analyse data, or to generate simulation results), or to build components of a research data infrastructure (e.g. a data repository).

Materials Any element of the research process that can be coded digitally or shared physically (e.g. protocols, survey questions, instructions, intervention materials, videos of the study procedure, specimens, reagents, samples, and other items used to collect data and/or conduct the research).

Preprint An article, book chapter, book, or other scholarly work that is deposited in a repository ahead of peer review. Equivalent terms used in some disciplines are 'working papers' and 'unpublished manuscripts'.

Preregistration The practice by which researchers specify elements of the planned work in a dedicated registry before observing the outcomes of the work. Examples include description of the planned approach for a qualitative study, and the data analysis plan for a quantitative study (i.e. a 'pre-analysis plan', which can be submitted either before the start of data collection or for previously collected datasets, before the start of data analysis).

Registered report A journal article format in which research question(s) and methodology are peer-reviewed before the work is conducted. A submission may be provisionally accepted for publication following peer-review, and eventually published if the authors follow through with the methodology specified in the accepted version (deviations from the registered plan are

allowed, but they must be explicitly justified and noted as such). Acceptance of the article to the journal is therefore independent of the results obtained.

Q4 Which of the following research practices are you aware of, and which do you have experience with? 'Aware only' indicates that the practice is applicable to your discipline, but you do not have direct experience with it. 'Accessing/using only' refers to resources made available by others. 'Practising myself' relates to implementation of the practice in your own research (in addition to, or instead of, accessing/using resources made available by others).

	Aware only	Accessing / using only	Practising myself	Not aware / not sure if applicable	Not applicable
Open Access publication	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data shared in repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Code shared in repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Materials shared in repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Preprint archived in repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Preregistration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Registered report	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q5 In your opinion, what would be the overall effect of widespread adoption of the following practices in your field of research?

	Detrimental	Neutral (neither detrimental nor beneficial)	Beneficial	Not sure	Not applicable
Open Access publication	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data shared in repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Code shared in repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Materials shared in repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Preprint archived in repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Preregistration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Registered report	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Change in research practices

This section relates to perceived barriers and potential downsides to the adoption of open research practices in your discipline.

Different factors may contribute to the adoption of open research practices, including:

- **infrastructure**, i.e. tools, resources, and/or services that enable implementation of the practice (e.g. repositories for digital or physical storage; registries for preregistration; publishing platforms or outlets) and of relevant community standards (e.g. guidelines relating to citation of data and metadata; ethical and legal guidelines for sharing sensitive data);
- **training**, i.e. the acquisition of knowledge and/or skills needed to implement the practice;
- **norms**, i.e. widespread attitudes and behaviours that support and/or encourage the practice (e.g. the perception that the field is aware of the practice and in favour of implementation; interest from early-career researchers; support from supervisors, mentors);
- **incentives**, i.e. resources and/or mechanisms that reward the practice (e.g. dedicated funding, awards; institutional recognition);
- **policy**, i.e. a requirement to implement the practice by relevant stakeholders (e.g. institutions, funders, publishers).

Time may be perceived as an additional factor contributing to adoption of a practice. Rather, we consider availability of time, or lack thereof, as a consequence of the factors listed above. For example, a researcher may choose to invest the time required to adopt a practice depending on:

- the availability of infrastructure or training, which facilitate implementation;
- the existence of norms in the community, which mitigate the burden on the researcher;
- the presence of incentives, or policy, which reward and/or mandate the practice in the researcher's field or institution.

Q6 Do you face any barriers in adopting the following practices and, if so, what are they? Tick all that apply and/or provide a brief description for any others.

	Infrastructure absent or limited	Training absent or limited	Norms absent or weak	Incentives absent or weak	Policy absent or weak	Other	No barriers	Not sure	Not applicable
Open Access publication	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ¹	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Data shared in repository	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ²	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Code shared in repository	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ³	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Materials shared in repository	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁴	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Preprint archived in repository	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁵	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Preregistration	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁶	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Registered report	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁷	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

¹Please provide a brief description for additional barriers regarding Open Access publication

²Please provide a brief description for additional barriers regarding Data shared in repository

³Please provide a brief description for additional barriers regarding Code shared in repository

⁴Please provide a brief description for additional barriers regarding Materials shared in repository

⁵Please provide a brief description for additional barriers regarding Preprint archived in repository

⁶Please provide a brief description for additional barriers regarding Preregistration

⁷Please provide a brief description for additional barriers regarding Registered report

Q7 In your view, are there any downsides to widespread adoption of the following practices in your field of research? If so, please provide a brief description.

	Yes	No	Not sure	Not applicable
Open Access publication	<input type="radio"/> ¹	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Data shared in repository	<input type="radio"/> ²	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Code shared in repository	<input type="radio"/> ³	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Materials shared in repository	<input type="radio"/> ⁴	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Preprint archived in repository	<input type="radio"/> ⁵	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Preregistration	<input type="radio"/> ⁶	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Registered report	<input type="radio"/> ⁷	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

¹Please provide a brief description of downsides to widespread adoption of Open Access publication in your field of research.

²Please provide a brief description of downsides to widespread adoption of Data shared in repository in your field of research.

³Please provide a brief description of downsides to widespread adoption of Code shared in repository in your field of research.

⁴Please provide a brief description of downsides to widespread adoption of Materials shared in repository in your field of research.

⁵Please provide a brief description of downsides to widespread adoption of Preprint archived in repository in your field of research.

⁶Please provide a brief description of downsides to widespread adoption of Preregistration in your field of research.

⁷Please provide a brief description of downsides to widespread adoption of Registered report in your field of research.

Recruitment criteria

This section relates to recruitment criteria in your field of research at Oxford, focusing on your perception of the criteria in use, and your views about which criteria *should* be used.

Q8 To the best of your knowledge, to what extent are the following criteria used for recruitment in your field of research at Oxford? Please list any additional criteria in the empty boxes below.

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Considerably	Not sure	Not applicable
Number of publications	<input type="radio"/>					
Prestige of publication outlet	<input type="radio"/>					
Quality of publications	<input type="radio"/>					
Authorship role (e.g. lead or senior author vs. contributing author)	<input type="radio"/>					
Citations (e.g. total number, <i>h</i> -index)	<input type="radio"/>					
Grant support (e.g. total amount, source)	<input type="radio"/>					
Impact (e.g. policy, medical applications, patents, media coverage)	<input type="radio"/>					
Teaching (e.g. amount, quality, creation of materials)	<input type="radio"/>					
Supervision, mentoring (e.g. amount, quality)	<input type="radio"/>					
Service to the profession (e.g. editorial work, contributions to the work of professional bodies or learned societies)	<input type="radio"/>					
Citizenship (e.g. involvement in	<input type="radio"/>					

departmental or University committees)						
National and/or international reputation (e.g. recognition, awards)	<input type="radio"/>					
Collaboration network (e.g. size, strength)	<input type="radio"/>					
Open research practices	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					
	<input type="radio"/>					

Q9 In your opinion, to what extent should the following criteria be used for recruitment in your field of research at Oxford? Please list any additional criteria in the empty boxes below.

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Considerably	Not sure	Not applicable
Number of publications	<input type="radio"/>					
Prestige of publication outlet	<input type="radio"/>					
Quality of publications	<input type="radio"/>					
Authorship role (e.g. lead or senior author vs. contributing author)	<input type="radio"/>					
Citations (e.g. total number, <i>h</i> -index)	<input type="radio"/>					
Grant support (e.g. total amount, source)	<input type="radio"/>					
Impact (e.g. policy, medical applications, patents, media coverage)	<input type="radio"/>					

Teaching (e.g. amount, quality, creation of materials)	o	o	o	o	o	o
Supervision, mentoring (e.g. amount, quality)	o	o	o	o	o	o
Service to the profession (e.g. editorial work, contributions to the work of professional bodies or learned societies)	o	o	o	o	o	o
Citizenship (e.g. involvement in departmental or University committees)	o	o	o	o	o	o
National and/or international reputation (e.g. recognition, awards)	o	o	o	o	o	o
Collaboration network (e.g. size, strength)	o	o	o	o	o	o
Open research practices	o	o	o	o	o	o
	o	o	o	o	o	o
	o	o	o	o	o	o
	o	o	o	o	o	o

Training and support needs

This section focuses on training and support needs relating to open research at Oxford.

Q10 For which of the following topics do you think more guidance is necessary? ‘No guidance needed’ indicates that sufficient guidance on the topic is available. ‘No guidance wanted’ indicates that you do not see the net benefit of engaging with the topic (e.g. it may be applicable to your field but you are not interested in the topic). Please list any additional topics in the empty boxes below.

	No guidance needed	No guidance wanted	Written guidance only	Written guidance and workshop-led training	Not sure	Not applicable
How to publish open access articles, theses, or monographs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How to prepare data management plans	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How to prepare data and metadata for archiving, and possibly for sharing in a public repository in line with community standards	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How to prepare ethics applications that allow archiving of anonymised data in a public repository	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How to write good quality code (including unit testing, version control, reproducible documentation) and share it publicly (e.g. selection of a repository that assigns a DOI)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How to prepare materials for sharing (e.g. in a digital repository that assigns a DOI, or in a physical repository)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How to choose and apply licences for sharing resources (e.g. data, materials, and/or code) and navigate relevant legislation (including copyright law, privacy and GDPR law, commercial law, and institutional regulations)	o	o	o	o	o	o
How to prepare preregistrations and/or registered reports (including experimental design, statistics, data simulation)	o	o	o	o	o	o
Guidance on sharing preprints (e.g. selection of appropriate repository, consideration of publisher's rights, ethical considerations)	o	o	o	o	o	o
How to assess job applications responsibly, fairly, and transparently	o	o	o	o	o	o
	o	o	o	o	o	o
	o	o	o	o	o	o
	o	o	o	o	o	o

Q11 What additional support would you find useful to implement open research practices? Please list any additional means of support in the empty boxes below.

	Not useful	Useful	Essential	Not sure
Seminars introducing relevant topics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Mentoring from an expert in your field who has experienced similar challenges and can provide specialist advice as needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coaching support from a trained coach who can help you explore options and identify what may work best for you to tackle either focused problems or strategic longer-term issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Support networks open to researchers from all career stages, with a focus on sharing experience and good practice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online resources collating case studies and tips	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Existing training

This final section focuses on training relating to open research that is *already* available at Oxford.

We aim to find out about all initiatives at Oxford, so that we can promote them to relevant groups. Those we are currently aware of are listed here:

<https://ox.ukrn.org/resources/>

<https://ox.ukrn.org/events/#initiatives>

Q12 Please provide information to help us identify initiatives at Oxford that relate to open research (e.g. courses, workshops, summer schools, working groups, study groups, meet-ups). You can add as many initiatives as you like by clicking the '+' symbol.

	Description (e.g. name of initiative, provider, contact, target audience, webpage, social media)
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Please contact the Reproducible Research Oxford Coordinator, Dr Malika Ihle (malika.ihle@anthro.ox.ac.uk), if you would like to suggest and contribute to a new initiative.

Thank you!

Thank you for completing the survey! The information you provided will contribute to shaping the implementation of open research practices and responsible research assessment at Oxford, and to the development of related training aimed at researchers. Relevant findings will be disseminated via the Reproducible Research Oxford [website](#).

For a list of **resources** providing guidance on open research practices at Oxford, please visit:

- <https://ox.ukrn.org/resources/>

Guidance on specific topics is available from the following resources:

Open Access publishing

- <http://openaccess.ox.ac.uk/>
- <http://openaccess.ox.ac.uk/open-access-at-oxford/>
- <https://osf.io/94rsp/>

Data sharing

- <https://researchdata.ox.ac.uk/>
- <https://fairsharing.org/>
- <https://osf.io/wp4zu/>

Code sharing

- <https://skills.it.ox.ac.uk/>
- <https://www.rse.ox.ac.uk/>
- <https://ox.ukrn.org/events/#The-Carpentries>
- <https://osf.io/qw9c>

Preprint archiving

- <https://osf.io/m4zyh/>

Preregistration and registered reports

- <https://osf.io/8v2n7/>

Responsible use of research metrics

- <https://researchsupport.admin.ox.ac.uk/information/principles>

For a list of **initiatives** promoting open research practices at Oxford, please visit:

- <https://ox.ukrn.org/events/#initiatives>

To find out about related **events and activities** organised by Reproducible Research Oxford, you can subscribe to our mailing list and follow us on Twitter:

- <https://web.maillist.ox.ac.uk/ox/subscribe/rroxford>
- https://twitter.com/RR_Oxford

As a **'thank you'** for completing the survey, we will donate £1 to the University's [Graduate Student Support Fund](#) (up to a total of £1,500).

Please [click here](#) for a chance to win one of five £50 [Bookshop.org](#)'s gift cards!

Clicking will open a new browser window featuring a separate secure form. In this form you can optionally provide your contact details to enter the raffle for the Blackwell's gift cards. The information provided through the form will not be linked to your survey responses in any way, and it will be permanently deleted once all raffle prizes are accepted. We will not use the information for any other purpose.

Thank you for completing the survey on open research at Oxford!

Here you can provide your contact details for a chance to win one of five £50 gift cards from Bookshop.org. This form is independent from the survey and any contact information you provide cannot be linked to your survey responses in any way. Your personal data will be stored securely, and it will be accessed exclusively to select winners through a raffle. The information will be permanently deleted once all raffle prizes are accepted, and it will not be used for any other purpose.

You can modify your contact details, and/or withdraw your consent, at any time until 1 March 2022 by contacting the Reproducible Research Oxford Coordinator, Dr Malika Ihle (malika.ihle@anthro.ox.ac.uk).

I consent to entering the raffle and to processing of the information I provide as outlined above.

Minimally, please enter either your email address or your phone number, so that we can notify you if you are selected as one of the winners.

Q1 Name (optional)

Q2 Email (optional)

Q3 Phone number (optional)

Good luck!

If you are selected as one of the five winners, you will be notified at the contact information provided by 15 March 2022.